

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Genetic studies of seed dormancy in high grain quality cultivars

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Rice varieties grown in wet season (He Thu) in the Mekong delta need to possess seed dormancy.

We studied the genetics of seed dormancy in crosses involving three varieties with grain dormancy and five without dormancy but with high grain quality. Two replications of 30 seeds each were grown in the greenhouse. Panicles were tagged as they emerged and harvested 30 d after flowering.

IR24 and OM80 are very susceptible to preharvest sprouting. Seed dormancy in the F₁ was not completely dominant (Table 1). However, KDML/OM80, KDML/IR64, and OM201/IR64 had

about 75% germination at 40 d after harvest (DAH).

Seed dormancy in the segregating F₂ populations at 10 DAH were tabulated as 0-25%, 26-50%, 51-75%, and 76-100% (Table 2). The F₂ from KDML/OM87-9, MTL 43/OM80, and OM201/OM87-9 segregated in the ratio of 3 dormant: 13 nondormant. This indicates control of dormancy by digenic recessive genes. Two duplicate recessive genes control dormancy in OM201/OM80.

The F₂ populations from KDML/OM80 and MTL 43/OM87-9 segregated in the ratio of 37:27 and 1:63, respectively, dormant to nondormant. This shows control of dormancy by trigenic gene action. ■

Table 1. Germination in the F₁ of rice hybrids and their parents (hull intact treatment) at 10-60 d after harvest.

Designation	Germination (%)					
	10	20	30	40	50	60
	<i>Cross</i>					
MTL 43/IR64	10	27	52	74	91	92
MTL 43/IR24	12	19	20	78	79	80
MTL 43/OM80	41	54	78	99		
MTL 43/OM86-9	16	30	64	78	94	98
MTL 43/OM87-9	22	42	73	81	98	
KDML/IR64	6	37	61	84	100	
KDML/IR24	40	69	88	93		
KDML/OM80	4	39	55	60	85	
KDML/OM86-9	25	44	76	88	90	
KDML/OM87-9	19	25	54	73	77	85
OM201/IR64	4	21	66	84	93	
OM201/IR24	15	36	70	90		
OM201/OM80	10	19	49	81	90	
OM201/OM86-9	13	31	48	74	93	
OM201/OM87-9	18	37	77	78	90	
	<i>Dormant parents</i>					
MTL 43	0	2	3	20	41	81
KDML	0	0	0			
OM201	0	5	28	49	51	75
	<i>Nondormant parents</i>					
IR64	30	48	72	88	99	
IR24	78	79	85	92		
OM80	60	79	92	100		
OM86-9	12	22	55	71	92	
OM87-9	40	65	92	96		

Table 2. Segregation for seed dormancy in the F₂ 10 days after harvest (hull intact treatment), by germination percentage.

Cross	F ₂ segregants (no.) by germination class				Ratio of 0-25:26-100 germination	χ^2	P
	0-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-100%			
KDML/OM87-9	21	14	31	58	3:13	0.27	0.75-0.50
KDML/OM80	180	33	24	63	37:27	0.59	0.50-0.25
MTL 43/OM87-9	4	20	44	232	1:63	0.10	0.75-0.50
MTL 43/OM80	58	63	61	118	3:13	0.70	0.90-0.75
OM201/OM87-9	62	55	67	116	3:13	0.72	0.50-0.25
OM201/OM80	21	29	43	207	1:15	0.29	0.75-0.50

Breeding methods

A supplementary pollination technique for hybrid rice seed production

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We monitored the flowering characters of CMS, maintainer, and restorer lines (V20A, V20B, Zhensan 97A, Zhensan 97B, IR26, R314, Zei 64-7, Zei 64-49, and R8312) 1987-89. Three samples of 30 plants each were examined for each line. Maintainer and restorer lines had one or two obvious flowering peaks in a day: 70-90% of the glumes flowered within these peaks (see figure). In lines with two peaks, each peak lasted 30-40 min; in lines with one peak, the peak lasted 40-60 min.

After glume opening, the anther exerted in 2-4 min, anther stalk elongated in 4-6 min, and pollen grains appeared in 7-8 min. Pollen grain spread followed the flowering peak, lasting for 10-15 min with two peaks and 20-30 min with one peak. In CMS lines, the flowering peak did not appear before the end of flowering of the male parents.

These results indicate that supplementary pollination during the pollen grain spreading peak of the male parent had more effect on seed yield than the previous method of pollinating each half hour from maternal flowering to end of flowering of male parent. Seed set increased more than 7.6% and seed yield 8%.

We devised a new technique for supplementary pollination. A nylon rope 0.4 cm in diameter is pulled at 1 m/s along the length of the plots, to scatter pollen grains during the spreading peak. This is carried out two times for each peak, at a 15-min interval, in double peaks; 3-4 times for only one peak. ■

Flowering curves of CMS, maintainer, and restorer lines. Lingling, Hunan, China, 1987-89.

F₁ fertility in indica/japonica crosses

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Low F₁ fertility in crosses of indica and japonica is still a problem. In 1988, we tested the F₁ fertility of two sets of combinations under irrigated conditions. One set was a direct japonica/indica cross (a native japonica variety was crossed with an exotic indica); the other was a modified japonica/indica cross (an advanced line or native japonica variety de-

rived from indica/ japonica was crossed with a japonica or an indica parent).

Modified japonicalindica crosses showed significantly higher spikelet fertility (74.1-90.25%) than the typical japonica/indica cross (9.75-35.75%) (see table).

The sterility of F₁ hybrids in direct indica/japonica cross was reportedly the result of genic or cryptic structural hybridity between chromosomes of the

indica and japonica varieties. We infer that the higher fertility in the modified japonicalindica crosses must be the result of the effectiveness of the advanced lines or native japonica varieties used as bridge parents. They presumably carry either dominant genes, to neutralize the effects of recessive complementary lethal genes in the indica and/or japonica variety, or wide compatible genes, to overcome the hybrid sterility barrier. ■

Comparison of F₁ fertility in japonica/indica crosses. Wuhan, China, 1988.

Cross	Fertility (%)
<i>Direct japonica/indica</i>	
LK58/IR36	9.75
HLR4/IR36	16.46
Gh 4/IR28	35.35
105/TKM6	19.82
H857/TKM6	24.23
Mean (x ₂)	21.22
LSD	9.59
<i>Modified japonica/indica</i>	
607 ^a /Longfu 6 ^b	86.53
607/Bamboo rice ^c	90.25
6107 ^a /VN51 ^c	77.70
6107/857 ^b	87.00
HLRS ^b /GS1 ^c	86.37
HLR5/I 636 ^c	74.10
Mean (x ₁)	83.66
LSD	6.28
t = 13.01 > 1% level	

^a Advanced line. ^b Japonica variety derived from an indica/ japonica cross. ^c Indica variety.

Use of male gametocide to induce complete male sterility in a partially male sterile rice

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Photoperiod-sensitive genic male-sterile rice (PGMSR) is also very sensitive to temperature. While photoperiod is relatively even from year to year, temperature is variable. This means a PGMSR grown in the summer can show variation in pollen sterility, making it unsuitable as female parent in hybrid seed production.

We evaluated a new indica PGMSR, CIS28-15, that was isolated from a B₉F₄ progeny of the cross Caloro/IR28. The critical stage of its sterility-transformation is about 20 Jul, with fertility-transformation 5 Sep under normal conditions in Xiangtan (29° N). But in 1989, male

sterility in the field was not complete between 20 Jul and 15 Aug because the air temperature was unusually low (mean 23 °C) and fluctuated widely.

We sought to induce complete pollen sterility by spraying the male gametocide (CH₃As O₃Zn.H₂O) in 30, 40, 50, and 60 ppm concentrations on the leaves of CIS28-15 at 5 d before heading. Other plants of CIS28-15 were sprayed with plain water. The experiment had four replications, with 20 hills of 1 plant each.

Initiation of panicle primordium starts about 30 d before heading. From 20 Jul to 15 Aug, we recorded the heading date of every panicle, including those of the main shoot and all tillers, to infer the development stage of each panicle when the plant was sprayed with the male gametocide. Observations on pollen and spikelet fertility were made on bagged panicles and open-pollinated panicles.

The results indicated the following (see table):